

DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION PLAN AND
REPORTS, INCLUDING NETWORK DEVELOPMENT —
VERSION 3
12/2024

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1. Executive summary

The third version of the “Dissemination & Communication plan and reports including network” deliverable sets out the strategy and main activities performed by the agrifood team in 2024 in terms of communicating its goals, outputs and impacts. It also describes how it is sharing its results and building a community.

In terms of planning, it defines specific actions and measures for all activities related to community building and practical assets key to ensuring the proper visibility of agrifoodTEF as one of the Testing and Experimentation Facilities projects.

The report also outlines agrifoodTEF stakeholder groups and targeted engagement activities with dedicated campaigns to increase the impact of communication and dissemination activities.

The document lays the foundations for future actions in three further documents (D5.1 V4 in 2025, D5.1 V5 in 2026 and D5.1 V6 in 2027), which will report on impacts and achievements and update plans with an increasing focus on how dissemination and communication activities can support the sustainability plan of agrifoodTEF.

The deliverable shows also how activities will be monitored through pre-defined KPIs coupled with qualitative assessments. It also provides a concise report on current achievements, upcoming synergies and knowledge sharing, as well as engagement roadmaps for the targeted stakeholders.

2. Introduction

This deliverable represents the third iteration of the plan for dissemination and communication activities. Its primary goal is to articulate the strategy and foreseen initiatives for the communication and dissemination efforts. The agrifoodTEF team aims to employ dedicated multichannel actions and campaigns to facilitate meaningful engagement with various stakeholder groups.

Following this deliverable, three subsequent updates of the report are scheduled for production in M36, M48 and M60.

2.1 Structure of the document

The document is structured into seven main sections that aim to provide a comprehensive overview of the communication and dissemination strategies and plans employed by the project:

- *Sections 2 and 3:* describe the general objectives of the deliverable.
- *Section 4:* presents the dissemination and communication strategy tailored for specific Stakeholder Groups (SGs).
- *Section 5:* details various campaigns designed to achieve communication and dissemination goals.
- *Section 6:* showcases the Communication and Dissemination plan, emphasising the channels and elements employed. It also explores the role of synergies in meeting communication and dissemination objectives.
- *Section 7:* discusses the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) implemented to monitor the quantitative impact of communication and dissemination strategies.
- *Section 8:* draws the conclusions and summarises the next steps.

3. Main objectives

As part of WP5, T5.3 leads the development, update and implementation of the dissemination and communication (D&C) strategy for agrifoodTEF. The main objectives of the D&C activities are as follows:

- Transfer the agrifoodTEF knowledge and results to relevant stakeholder groups;
- Raise awareness and openly demonstrate clear environmental, social, economic and technological benefits of adopting AI and robotics in the agritech sector;
- Maximise the impact of research and enable the value of results to go beyond agrifoodTEF and its immediate end users.

Through the activities described in this deliverable, the D&C team will stimulate outreach towards different types of stakeholders and enhance the impact of project results beyond the consortium boundaries to promote uptake and innovation, in support of the overall objectives:

- To build an agile and sustainable network that provides world class expertise and state of the art infrastructure for the design and the implementation of AI testing and experimenting methodologies in real-world environments and to guarantee the long-term sustainability of the network;
- To provide services to technology providers in testing, experimenting, certifying and validating AI, data and robotics solutions;

- To foster trust and acceptance in the user community and to boost the roll-out of European AI, data, and robotics solutions from the lab to the market, guaranteeing maturity of the solutions through high quality validation processes;
- To ensure the trust of technology providers when using agrifoodTEF services;
- To strengthen and expand the agrifoodTEF network to cover the European market;
- To offer and further develop end-user driven use cases and methodologies to guarantee the involvement of smaller farms and businesses, with specific focus on affordability of AI solutions.

4. Dissemination and Communication Strategy

The agrifoodTEF project’s communication and dissemination strategy, part of WP5’s focus on “**Ecosystem and Market Development and Visibility**,” is designed to deliver a coordinated and effective 60-month plan, guided by the SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic, and Timely) approach.

Communication Activities

- Developing a consistent visual identity.
- Maintaining an informative project website.
- Designing and distributing event materials.
- Leveraging social media for updates.
- Creating engaging videos.
- Sharing press releases for key milestones.

Dissemination Activities

- Publishing research findings.
- Participating in conferences.
- Participating or attending relevant tradeshows.
- Organising practical demonstrations and workshops for users and adopters.

Engagement Activities

- Attending industry events.
- Hosting workshops for in-depth discussions.
- Providing webinars and training materials to share knowledge.
- Face to face meetings with companies with a focus on AI and/or robots

Success is measured through website traffic, social media engagement, stakeholder feedback, publications, presentations, collaborations, and network growth.

Communication Team

In order to share the most relevant outcomes and evaluate the performance of the D&C activities, from September 2024, a communication team was established, with members from each agrifoodTEF node (national bodies supporting local companies and developers during testing and validation).

The team aims to:

- Improve local communication strategies.
- Share best practices.
- Monitor communication KPIs and enhance performance where needed.
- Ensure quality standards for dissemination materials in both content and layout.

As of December 2024, the team has implemented procedures for managing social media channels, publishing website content, organising events, and developing flyers.

The team meets monthly to ensure alignment, strategy refinement, and updates on progress.

4.1 Diversification across Stakeholder Groups

agrifoodTEF is dedicated to establishing a robust and dynamic ecosystem that fosters collaboration and connectivity among a wide network of stakeholders, contributing to the overall success of the project. By leveraging multiple sector-specific TEF networks, agrifoodTEF aims to create opportunities for meaningful connections, exchange of best practices, and enhanced collaborative efforts.

To achieve the goal of promoting effective and fruitful engagement among diverse stakeholder groups, it is essential to involve end-users, regulatory bodies, supply chains, and civil society organisations in both the innovation and testing processes. Each node within the network will serve as a "living laboratory," actively learning and evolving in its function. This approach will ensure that stakeholder participation is seamlessly integrated into the TEF development process, thereby enriching the testing environments with controlled and realistic scenarios.

agrifoodTEF will implement a tailored engagement strategy for each of its six target audience groups to maximise their contributions and benefits.

1. Farmers and Advisors

As one of the primary stakeholder groups of agrifoodTEF, farmers and their advisors are regarded as the principal clients of the services provided. This group will benefit from continuously updated and developed use cases, supported by annual workshops on technology and use cases. agrifoodTEF thrives on the insights provided by farmers, which directly inform the project's outcomes and are subsequently applied in real-world situations. The active involvement of farmers ensures that the project remains grounded in practical relevance, aligning its innovations with the needs of its end users.

2. Farmers Associations

Farmers' associations represent an influential stakeholder group with a vested interest in the latest advancements and technological applications offered by agrifoodTEF. Serving as amplifiers, these associations can broaden outreach and integrate additional farmers into the project ecosystem. Through their involvement, agrifoodTEF can extend the reach of its workshops, training sessions, and services, ensuring a wider adoption of innovative solutions across the agricultural community.

3. Public Administration and Governmental Bodies

Public administration entities and governmental bodies are pivotal to the agrifoodTEF initiative. The TEF provides an ideal platform for establishing streamlined clearance processes for cutting-edge robotics and AI solutions, particularly long-term autonomous machinery. Moreover, agrifoodTEF seeks to enhance awareness of the transformative impact the TEF can have on the agricultural sector. The co-funding and active participation of local governments associated with the project nodes and satellites underscore its significance as a public-private collaboration driving innovation.

4. Research Institutes

agrifoodTEF actively targets research institutions to engage in the project, recognising their vital role in the development, testing, monitoring, and refinement of technologies and services. By bridging the gap between academic research and practical applications, these institutes can help enhance the quality and scope of services provided to stakeholders. Their involvement ensures the incorporation of cutting-edge advancements, contributing to the continuous evolution of the TEF's offerings. Furthermore, their participation enables the integration of the TEF into broader research and development initiatives, fostering a cycle of innovation and application.

5. Machinery Suppliers

For machinery suppliers, the TEF offers a specialised infrastructure to test, evaluate, and integrate technological solutions into their products. This collaboration between suppliers and research institutions facilitates the development of technologically advanced machinery tailored to meet end-user needs. The expertise and resources of machinery suppliers play a crucial role in the design, implementation, and refinement processes, ensuring that products align with customer demands and contribute effectively to the project's goals.

agrifoodTEF's multifaceted engagement strategy ensures that each stakeholder group plays an active and complementary role in advancing the project's mission, thereby fostering a vibrant, innovative, and sustainable agrifood ecosystem.

6. Technology Providers and AI, robotics and Data intermediaries

To foster trust in the agri-food sector and support technology providers, especially SMEs and start-ups, the agrifoodTEF project offers facilities to test and experiment with advanced AI-based solutions. A supervised regulatory sandbox framework is provided to assist nodes and satellites in establishing AI regulatory burdens for SMEs and start-ups. Intellectual property (IP) support is key to helping SMEs, the primary agrifoodTEF clients, valorise intangible assets, ensuring a sustainable business model that accelerates digital transition. agrifoodTEF helps European SMEs protect and capitalise on their IP, while offering services at reduced internal cost prices. Each service is treated as a project, boosting competitiveness for technology providers and agri-food sector players, while delivering societal benefits. By enabling AI and robotics start-ups, as well as agriculture machine manufacturers, to bring precise, effective solutions to market, agrifoodTEF lays the foundation for a new generation of data-driven decision support systems and agri-food robots.

Figure 1 – agrifoodTEF’s Stakeholder Groups

5. Campaigns

The D&C strategy is built upon four campaigns that run throughout the entire project lifetime. The campaigns help increase visibility of the project’s results, support its sustainability plan and engage with identified stakeholder groups. Furthermore, they help ensure that the project’s goals and objectives are aligned with the overarching goal of building European Testing and Experimentation Facilities for agrifood Innovation.

Campaign #1 AWARENESS
Increase the awareness of the targeted stakeholders about the agrifoodTEF project

Purpose: This campaign aims to increase the all the relevant stakeholder's awareness on the project by communicating, with a consistent visual identity, the project’s domains of interest, targeted communities, addressed challenges, activities, events, future outputs and expected impacts to attract them to “visit” the project’s communication channels, such as the website or social media channels.

Target stakeholders: All stakeholders

Timeline: M01 – M60

ACTION	ACTIVITY
Project branding	agrifoodTEF visual identity, consolidating awareness among relevant communities. Specific messaging will be tailored to target key audiences, using call-to-actions and

	branded communications that resonate with them the most. Promotional material will be designed and distributed.
Project's website	SEO-Driven Website showcasing project's assets, outputs and events, where all marketing activities are coordinated for a usercentric experience (UX). Achieving strong engagement through conversion-rate optimisation (CRO). All website analytics will be gathered on a customised dashboard.
Social media	The official LinkedIn, Twitter / X, Instagram, Facebook and YouTube channels will serve to engage stakeholders via multimedia campaigns, one-to-one interactions and live project's events covering.
Newsletters	Provide key updates about the project's activities, upcoming events and outputs via email in a reader-friendly format.
Press Releases	Dissemination of newsworthy project results or events to engage relevant media and publishers in the agritech field.
Videos	Custom-designed videos to raise awareness about the challenges and benefits offered by the agrifoodTEF services.
Ads campaigns	Advertisement campaigns to broaden the project community through increased social media reach, and YouTube views which will turn in higher engagement.

Table 1 – Campaign #1 Awareness

Campaign #2 INTEREST Onboard the stakeholders in the project's community	
Purpose: This campaign will produce tailored, in-depth communication materials designed to highlight agrifoodTEF's key outcomes, benefits, and innovative applications in the agritech sector. The communication approach will be customised for each stakeholder group, ensuring the messaging aligns with their specific interests and resonates with the type of information most relevant to them.	
Target stakeholders: All stakeholders	
Timeline: M01 – M60	
ACTION	ACTIVITY
3rd Party events participation	Participation in relevant 3rd-party events to increase the project's outreach potential by tapping into their communities. During the 3rd-party events agrifoodTEF will share its addressed challenges, highlighting its potential for the circularity of the industrial community, showcase its results and expected impacts.
8 Webinars	The project will organise a series of webinars to provide additional in-depth content and insights about the project solutions, results, expected impacts, novel AI and robotics applications in the agritech field.
Open access publications based on the agrifoodTEF main results	Delivery of papers and articles for journals to disseminate the new knowledge, the scientific/technical innovation produced and its benefits for the society.

Table 2 – Campaign #2 Interest

Campaign #3 CONSIDERATION
Identify and attract the leads within the project’s community

Purpose: This campaign will onboard end-users to test and experiment digital services and tease the members of the project’s community with more hands-on practical content from the project’s success stories and lessons learned to turn them into leads, stakeholders' part of the agrifoodTEF’s community who have shown active interest in the project’s solutions and could thus become customers.

Target stakeholders: All stakeholders

Timeline: M18 – M60

ACTION	ACTIVITY
Success Stories development	Informative news pieces and videos exploring the challenges and solutions involved in implementing AI and robotics in the agritech sector.
Organisation and participation in workshops with other TEF projects	Dedicated workshops to showcase the lessons learned and the impact of the TEF projects main results.
Organisation of workshops for small farms and businesses	Dedicated workshops designed to engage digital SMEs, start-ups, and farmers, promoting the adoption of TEF principles to drive the local implementation of digital solutions.

Table 3 – Campaign #3 Consideration

Campaign #4 CONVERSION
Convert the community members leads into clients

Purpose: This campaign aims to deliver targeted, content-rich dissemination materials to identified leads. By aligning with their commercial needs, the materials will showcase the societal, economic, and technological benefits of the project's solutions, with the goal of converting these leads into clients and distributors of TEF agritech services.

Target stakeholders: All stakeholders

Timeline: M18 – M60

ACTION	ACTIVITY
Training materials	Creation of training materials to enhance understanding and promote the sharing of best practices for adopting digital solutions in agriculture.
Workshops with EDIH	Collaborative workshops with European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIH) to co-develop training materials aimed at bridging the knowledge gap and facilitating the adoption of digital solutions in agriculture. The meetings are organised online and face to face.

Table 4 – Campaign #4 Conversion

6. Communication and Dissemination Plan

To achieve its objectives and maximise impact, agrifoodTEF has implemented a 60-month strategy designed to support its dissemination and communication goals, drawing on the extensive expertise within the project consortium. Throughout the project's duration, all partners contribute to community development and stakeholder engagement as an integral part of the communication plan. This continuous effort is key to enabling the dissemination and exploitation of project results, with partners committed to these activities both during and beyond the project's lifecycle.

The dissemination and communication plan focuses on broadening the project's reach, particularly emphasising the economic, societal, and environmental benefits agrifoodTEF offers to the agriculture sector. The overall plan aims to:

- Establish an active network that facilitates engagement and collaboration among identified stakeholder groups.
- Collaborate with related projects in the TEF domain, as well as those in cloud and edge computing, data spaces, artificial intelligence, robotics, and agricultural data, to enhance the development and adoption of TEF services.

6.1 Channels and elements

agrifoodTEF employs diverse communication channels, leveraging the extensive network of project partners. Communication channels refer to the means through which information is conveyed. In our case, these channels include platforms like social media, newsletters, and direct outreach.

The project aims to create tailored communication formats for different stakeholder groups. Communication elements are the specific pieces of content or information used in these formats. For instance, these elements could be articles, videos, or infographics designed to suit the preferences and interests of specific audiences.

The consortium boasts significant expertise and experience in developing communication and dissemination strategies. Through multichannel actions, agrifoodTEF reaches out to a broad range of stakeholders, media, professional networks, and social channels. Multichannel actions involve using various platforms simultaneously to maximise reach and impact.

The multichannel approach focuses on various tools and initiatives to foster community-building and engagement. This might include interactive webinars, engaging social media campaigns, or collaborative events to actively involve stakeholders.

In the table below, it is possible to find the channels used by the project team, a sample of elements, and the impact generated by each channel in advancing the dissemination and communication plan. This table provides a comprehensive overview of how different communication tools and content contribute to our overall strategy.

Channel	Sample of elements	Impact
Website	News pieces, PRs, videos, visuals, infographics, newsletters	The Drupal based website is the public hub of the project with all results disseminated there.

Social media	Videos, visuals, infographics	LinkedIn, Twitter/X, Facebook, Instagram and YouTube are harnessed to drive relevant, high-intent traffic to the project’s website. Posts will be made using relevant hashtags and UTMs (Urchin Tracking Modules) created specifically for each post and channel to track site traffic. The UTM parameters included in a URL serve to identify the marketing campaign responsible for driving traffic to a particular website. Additionally, they assign the website session of the browser, as well as any subsequent sessions within the campaign attribution window, to that campaign.
Emails	Newsletters	A branded email marketing service, which with its regular issues will become a solid channel that agrifoodTEF will leverage, to increase the community of end-users and adopters of TEF solutions.
Workshops	Brochures, roll-up banners, branded gadgets, videos	Physical and online workshops will be delivered to disseminate the agrifoodTEF main results and best practices.
Webinars	Banners, videos	8 webinars will take place during the project to showcase the main results achieved by agrifoodTEF
3 rd -party events	Brochures, roll-up banners, branded gadgets, videos	Participation at 3rd-party events serves to showcase the project’s main results to people outside the consortium and external players.
Ads campaigns	Videos, visuals, infographics	Ads campaigns have the objective to broaden stakeholder reach, increase subscribers to the newsletter, followers to the social media channels and increase the website views.

Table 5 – agrifoodTEF’s channels and elements

6.1.1 agrifoodTEF website

A [website](#)'s presence and ongoing development are crucial for ensuring a project's visibility and effective communication. As the primary source of information for external stakeholders, it allows the target audience to access relevant content, understand the project's value proposition, and discover opportunities for engagement.

For the agrifoodTEF project, which targets enterprises in the agricultural and food sectors, the website’s usability and resource discoverability are essential for achieving its goals. Smooth navigation is critical to ensuring users can easily find services and resources.

Initially, the project launched a landing page with external navigation options to access services. However, a preliminary analysis revealed that the website’s structure limited the user experience, making it difficult to navigate available resources easily.

As a result, the goal of the new website development was to provide enhanced capabilities, intuitive navigation, and more advanced functionalities that would increase agrifoodTEF's online visibility while offering a comprehensive overview of ongoing activities and available services.

6.1.1.1 UX/UI workshop

Following an initial assessment of the project’s strengths, value proposition, and the previous Catalogue features, Trust-IT Services organized a UX/UI workshop with all internal stakeholders. The aim was to identify challenges, priorities, and areas for improvement based on the analysis.

The workshop, structured in seven stages, focused on gathering feedback to refine the website's functionality and navigation. Partners were tasked with identifying key stakeholder groups, which led to prioritizing two main user categories: technology providers, AI, robotics, and data intermediaries, and “end users” within the agri-food ecosystem (farmers, advisors, and their associations).

The next phase involved evaluating the website's weaknesses in terms of structure, content, and functionality. A major concern was the difficulty in discovering the Catalogue and its associated services, which undermined the site's value proposition. Additionally, the Catalogue’s categorization made navigation challenging, and the overall structure lacked a logical flow. Other issues included the absence of a clear call to action, insufficient project content, and weak visual design.

Following the assessment, workshop participants worked to refine the website’s menu, eliminating redundancies and identifying priority sections. Notably, the Catalogue, Events, Success Stories, and Contact Us sections were highlighted for inclusion in the redesigned site.

Figure 2 – Main navigation menu of the previous agrifoodTEF website

When analysing the previous homepage, participants identified areas that required attention to enhance the user experience. The addition of a prominent call to action—directing users to the Catalogue of services—was seen as a priority. The section displaying node leaders was deemed unnecessary for external users, as it did not provide added value. Instead, suggestions were made to improve the interactive map of Europe and enhance scrolling functionality.

Assignment 7

SERVICES

Look at the image below.
How would you organize the services in the Catalogue?
What are the main service categories?
What filters are missing for an effective search?

Figure 4 – Brainstorming session on services visualization during the UX/UI workshop

6.1.1.2 Development of the new agrifoodTEF website with improved user experience

The design of the new website was based on the insights obtained from the UX/UI workshop and the overall assessment of the previous website's functionalities and the project's objectives. By analysing the potential users' needs, significant shortcomings in the website's usability were identified, which was also confirmed by the internal stakeholders. To propose a new website design that would address the existing pain points and ease the customer journey, a multistep design process was followed.

To start with, the results of the UX/UI workshop were analysed and divided into categories of issues to be addressed. These included the navigation menu, access to the Catalogue of Services, consistency in the services categorization and description, presentation of the project's mission, display of the opportunities for engagement and events promoted by the project, the overall information architecture, and development of a website with dedicated sections instead of a single landing page. This first stage was necessary to ensure no issue was overlooked and there was a clear focus on user needs.

Next, the work proceeded toward the definition of the sitemap and information architecture. The primary focus has been to provide easy navigation to the Catalogue and help users identify the right service based on their needs. To achieve this, it was envisaged to include a redirection to the Catalogue from the Homepage and suggest relevant services throughout the user journey. Furthermore, the insights provided in D1.2 served as the basis for the services

categorization in the Catalogue. To provide a clear overview of the project’s objectives and the parties involved, it was proposed to remove the nodes list from the Homepage and include a more structured description in a dedicated section, “About Us.” Based also on the partners’ insights, it was envisaged to include several points with contact information and a redirection to the contact form.

Figure 5 – Proposed sitemap for the new agrifoodTEF website

Following the sitemap development, the design process transitioned to the ideation phase. This included the creation of low-fidelity wireframes aimed at conveying the webpage structure and information hierarchy. The main goal was to validate the basic elements of the different website areas, such as the navigation, content blocks, and layout, and iterate on them in case of usability issues. The iterated wireframes played an important role in bridging the conceptualization phase to the development stage and suggesting a refined interaction flow compared to the previous website. From the set of developed wireframes, the work continued toward the production of high-fidelity mock-ups and prototypes.

Figure 6 – Wireframes of the new agrifoodTEF website

Prior to the transition from wireframes to mock-ups, a design system was developed to ensure that the new website is aligned with the project branding and that there is consistency across all areas. For this, the following elements were developed: colour and typography systems, components library, grid guidelines, and icon set.

Colour System

Typography

Figure 7 – Colour and typography system

Based on the design system, a high-fidelity mock-up has been designed to provide a visual representation of the new website prior to the development.

Figure 8 – High-fidelity mock-ups of the new agrifoodTEF website

As a result, the first version of the website included the Homepage, Catalogue of Services with dedicated service pages, a section "About Us" covering the project's mission and objectives with a redirection to the Nodes pages, an area for news and events, and a "Contact Us" form.

Figure 9 – New Catalogue of Services available on the agrifoodTEF website

The Catalogue of Services, which represents a central point of interest for users given the project’s value proposition, has been designed with particular attention to the user flow. With several entry points from the Homepage, as well as from the “About Us” section and service pages, the Catalogue showcases the service listing and a set of filters, which are displayed in a hierarchical manner. To facilitate navigation and search, the primary set of filters covers the targeted sectors, which include arable farming, food processing, greenhouse horticulture, livestock farming, tree crops, and viticulture. Next, the user is offered three additional sets of filters based on the type of product to validate, test, or evaluate, the type of service needed, and the location where the service is provided. All the filters have been based on the information provided in D1.2. The Catalogue also offers a search by keywords and information on the services’ customisation.

Figure 10 – Services suggestion on the website Homepage

In the upcoming months, it is envisaged that the improvement of the agrifoodTEF website will continue based on the users’ needs and the project’s objectives. The next steps will include the release of a dedicated area for training materials and an infrastructure catalogue to provide additional value to the website visitors.

6.1.2 Social media channels

Social media accounts play a pivotal role in agrifoodTEF dissemination and communication strategy, reaching out well beyond professionals in the agritech industries. The AI, robotics and agritech solutions represent a trending topic of conversation also in terms of social interest. While the adoption of digital solutions is increasingly attracting the interest and attention not only of sectoral players but also of the wider public, the adoption of digital solutions for farmers spans 21% (McKinsey)¹. This determines both main opportunities and challenges for the communication activities.

The social media channels are an instant form of communication with community members and potentially interested people or organisations. To help ensure continual visibility of the project’s efforts to targeted stakeholders like webinars, workshops or general events and announcements, agrifoodTEF uses the following social media channels: Twitter / X, LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook and YouTube, all characterised by the coordinated branding.

Figure 11 – agrifoodTEF social media banner

¹ <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/agriculture/our-insights/agtech-breaking-down-the-farmer-adoption-dilemma>

To give more visibility to the work agrifoodTEF is carrying out, starting from July 2024, the team has implemented a widespread and detailed social media strategy, with different social media accounts for each agrifoodTEF nodes. Each node country has its own social media channels where specific contents in local languages are communicated and national events are promoted.

In order to keep track of the social media activity - both the general one and the nodes' one - agrifoodTEF has implemented an Editorial Plan with weekly updates on social media posting. Section 6.1.2.7 will present in more detail the way of working implemented to disseminate the agrifoodTEF main achievements.

In general, the social media strategy adopted so far consists of weekly posts on each social media account - generally discussing and promoting the same topic.

6.1.2.1 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is the most recognised social media channel for building professional networking. The agrifoodTEF LinkedIn account (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/agrifoodtef>) is particularly useful to reach out to researchers, professionals and TEF customers in the field and share with them the project advancements. The possibility to tag, among others, partners, industry leaders, researchers and guest speakers with their professional profile increases the chances of visibility within their respective networks, allowing agrifoodTEF to reach related audiences and potentially new users and/or customers. This channel is usually updated with 1 to 2 posts per week, depending on the needs of the project. The communication on LinkedIn profile is run in English, even though nodes' LinkedIn profiles have been created to share updates in local languages as well.

Figure 12 – some printscreens of LinkedIn posts

As of today, the agrifoodTEF LinkedIn page counts 1261 followers - a continuously growing number, nourished by regular posting schedule and content-rich posts.

The table below presents the main LinkedIn KPIs related to the period January – December 2024.

Month	Followers' growth	Impressions	Clicks	Reactions	Reposts	Engagement rate
Jan-24	52	385	34	4	0	0.6
Feb-24	58	2835	70	68	1	0.03
Mar-24	54	1412	39	22	1	0.03
Apr-24	31	115	16	0	0	0.04
May-24	25	159	0	0	0	0
Jun-24	89	6081	427	181	2	0.09
Jul-24	136	10800	269	244	3	0.05
Aug-24	43	4594	196	142	5	0.06
Sep-24	76	4576	202	145	2	0.06
Oct-24	83	6885	579	266	1	0.1
Nov-24	44	4251	369	146	5	0.09
Dec-24	49	3200	155	133	4	0.08

Table 6 – LinkedIn KPIs from January to December 2024

The KPIs demonstrate a steady growth in followers, as highlighted in the table, with significant improvements in impressions, clicks, reactions, reposts, and engagement rates since the summer. This growth coincides with the implementation of a new, node-level social media strategy by the communication team. By increasing posting frequency and sharing more content-rich and relevant materials, agrifoodTEF has successfully attracted a more engaged audience, genuinely interested in its activities. Consequently, the number of followers continues to rise steadily.

6.1.2.2 X/Twitter

X/Twitter account @AgrifoodTEF (<https://x.com/AgrifoodTEF>) is the channel mainly used for quick and general communication about the project as well as the most frequently updated (with 1 to 2 tweets per week), through captivating visuals and to-the-point messaging.

The project will especially exploit popular hashtags such as #digital, #ai, #robotics and the ones related to the project like #agrifoodtef, #farming, #agritech.

Live tweeting at webinars, workshops, or other physical events is another important pillar of agrifoodTEF presence on this channel, as it helps make the feed more dynamic and allows different users to find out about the project.

The account was opened in June 2024, following the new multi-social media strategy implemented by the team to increase the reach and impact generated by the project.

101100622/agrifoodTEF

Figure 13 – some examples of X posts

The main statistics of X are summarised below:

Figure 14 – Number of X impressions in the period June – December 2024

Figure 15 – Number of new followers on X in the period June – December 2024

Figure 16 – Engagement rate on X in the period June – December 2024

The total number of followers on X is 48, which is significantly lower than LinkedIn, primarily due to the fact that the account was launched in June 2024, whereas the LinkedIn account has been active for over a year and a half.

While the number of followers has not seen a consistent increase, the engagement rate has risen. This indicates that the followers who have joined are genuinely interested in agrifoodTEF's objectives, leading to a more engaged and committed audience.

6.1.2.3 Facebook

Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/people/Agrifoodtef/61561389445661/>) is mainly used as a social media platform for advising and reaching the general public - such as public administrations and farmers associations. Also in this case, this platform has been implemented later on in June 2024, and currently we have reached 15 followers. The social media activity in this case has been focused on the general promotion of the project, with references and links to the website.

The statistics below showcase the results in terms of views, followers and visits reached so far.

Figure 17- Facebook statistics in the period June – December 2024

6.1.2.4 Instagram

Instagram (https://www.instagram.com/agrifood_tef/) is mainly used for social media posts mainly addressed to a younger audience - mainly students, young farmers and researchers. This platform was introduced in June 2024, together with Facebook and X/Twitter. Here, the audience reached so far counts 47 followers - a bit higher compared to Facebook. The goal here is to create contents with Instagram cards and reels providing clear and concise information, with references to the website contents and the services offered by agrifoodTEF.

Figure 18 – Overview of the Instagram feed

The statistics below showcase the results in terms of views, followers and visits reached so far.

Figure 19 – Instagram statistics in the period June – December 2024

6.1.2.5 YouTube

YouTube is the main repository for agrifoodTEF videos - which includes interviews, video-animations, recordings of online events and so on.

So far, the channel has been quite populated and it's currently divided into 2 main playlists:

- About agrifoodTEF: this playlist contains a short introductory video of agrifoodTEF project and a short video-interview to the project's coordinator overviewing the main goals of the project;
- agrifoodTEF Nodes: here, we have a collection of videos made by the Italian and Belgian nodes on the services offered.

The video material is going to be reused on other platforms via sharing or embedding, especially on agrifoodTEF website and social media channels to increase the number of visualisation and engagement with the community. Visibility is also attained thanks to suggestions in the "related videos" via the use of relevant keywords in the fields of artificial intelligence, robotics and agritech for titles and descriptions.

The YouTube channel currently hosts 7 videos recorded during the first two years of the project. These videos include interviews with project members and general informational content on agrifoodTEF's main objectives. The total number of video views has surpassed 980 over the past two years.

About agrifoodTEF ▶ Play all

agrifoodTEF - Synergy Days 2024 (Barcelona)

agrifoodTEF
5 views • 2 weeks ago

Digital success stories - AI Testing and Experimentatio...

agrifoodTEF
67 views • 4 months ago

AgrifoodTEF in a nutshell

agrifoodTEF
683 views • 1 year ago

agrifoodTEF Nodes ▶ Play all

The CIMAT robot and Treebot from ILVO

agrifoodTEF
39 views • 4 months ago

agrifoodTEF - Test and Experiment Facility at ILVO

agrifoodTEF
62 views • 5 months ago

FBK rover for digital mapping of experimentation fields

agrifoodTEF
72 views • 11 months ago

The Italian Node of agrifoodTEF in a nutshell

agrifoodTEF
55 views • 1 year ago

Figure 20 – Videos uploaded to the agrifoodTEF’s YouTube channel

6.1.2.6 Zenodo

Zenodo is the open repository of the project, where all the main reports and publications are collected with a publicly available Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to make the upload easily and uniquely citeable (and findable). Here, the community of experts and specialists will collect scientific papers, project publications and all the documents necessary for the dissemination of the project’s results.

agrifoodTEF has opened the Zenodo account in July 2024 mostly for:

- making the project’s outputs publicly accessible to the European research community,
- easing the process of finding and citing the project’s documents thanks to the DOI (Digital Object Identifier),
- facilitating the search for specific documents through the use of keyword-based searches. For agrifoodTEF, the keywords include AI, agritech, farming, robotics, agriculture, agrifood, farm, and digitalsolutions.
- promoting transparency and reproducibility by making data and results publicly available,
- creating the Zenodo project’s community to organise, store and showcase all project-related outputs in one unique repository.

agrifoodTEF

The European Testing and Experimentation Facilities for Agrifood Innovation.

Project <https://www.agrifoodtef.eu/>

Figure 21 – agrifoodTEF community on Zenodo

At the time of writing this deliverable, the Zenodo account hosts nine flyers developed to promote the work carried out by the nodes. In the future, Zenodo will also store post-event reports and publications created by the team.

6.1.2.7 Social media management across the agrifoodTEF nodes

As briefly explained in Section 6.1.2, the agrifoodTEF community is primarily divided into nine distinct nodes. To enhance the accessibility of the social media strategy for local teams, an internal communication officer team was established in July 2024. This team comprises at least one representative from each node and meets monthly to align on strategies for promoting their respective node’s objectives.

To support this localised approach, the team agreed to structure the social media strategy around nine distinct channels, as summarised in the table below.

Country	Communication team	Social media channels managed	Links	Language	Scope
Austria	Cornelius Riautschnig (Josephinum)	LinkedIn Austria	https://www.linkedin.com/company/agrifoodtef-austria/	German	Promotion of the Austrian services and participation to main events
Belgium	Laurens Van De Wiele (ILVO)	LinkedIn Belgium	https://www.linkedin.com/company/agrifoodtef-vlaanderen/	Dutch English	Promotion of the Belgian services and participation to main events
Denmark	Kit Krüger (Teknologisk)	LinkedIn Denmark	The LinkedIn account will be created in January 2025	Danish	Promotion of the Danish services and participation

					to main events
France	Ankur Mahtani (LNE)	LinkedIn France	https://www.linkedin.com/company/agrifoodtef-france/	France	Promotion of the France services and participation to main events
Italy	Pietro Barbieri (FBK) Teresa Ridolfi (Trust-IT)	LinkedIn Italy	https://www.linkedin.com/company/agrifoodtef-italia/	Italian	Promotion of the Italian services and participation to main events
Poland	Joanna Czarnecka–Musiał (Lukasiewicz)	LinkedIn Poland Facebook Poland	https://www.linkedin.com/company/agrifoodtef-polska/ https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61559633212170	Polish	Promotion of the Polish services and participation to main events
Spain	Paula Tosar (Gradiant) Pablo Godon Danza (Gradiant)	LinkedIn Spain	https://www.linkedin.com/company/agrifoodtefes/	Spanish	Promotion of the Spanish services and participation to main events
Sweden	Anna Hankers (RISE) Lina Katarina Heldmark (RISE) Sofia Pettersson (RISE)	LinkedIn Sweden	https://www.linkedin.com/company/agrifoodtef-sverige/	Swedish	Promotion of the Swedish services and participation to main events
The Netherlands	Mashiat Hossain (WUR)	LinkedIn the Netherlands	https://www.linkedin.com/company/agrifoodtef-nederland/	Dutch English	Promotion of the Dutch services and participation to main events

European account	Teresa Ridolfi (Trust-IT) Rita Giuffrida (Trust-IT)	Linkedin general account X general account Instagram general account Facebook general account	https://www.linkedin.com/company/agrifoodtef https://x.com/AgrifoodTEF https://www.instagram.com/agrifood_tef/ https://www.facebook.com/people/Agrifoodtef/61561389445661/	English	Promotion of the overall agrifoodTEF services and participation to main events
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Each social media account promotes its node’s services, national events, and initiatives in the local language. This approach ensures that audiences in each country receive targeted, tailored content from the national channels while also benefiting from broader, European-level updates on the project’s goals and activities via the central social media accounts.

To ensure consistency and coordination across the nine nodes, agrifoodTEF has implemented a joint Editorial Plan. This plan tracks all updates and ensures a steady flow of promotional content across the nodes.

Currently, Denmark is the only country without a dedicated social media account, as it joined the network at the end of 2024. Plans are in place to establish a dedicated channel for Denmark in 2025, enabling it to fully participate in the coordinated communication strategy.

As part of the social media management strategy for the nodes, the team decided to prioritize LinkedIn in 2024, based on its performance on the general agrifoodTEF channels. However, depending on the performance of other platforms on the main agrifoodTEF social media accounts, the team will evaluate the possibility of launching local Facebook, Instagram, or X channels in 2025.

6.1.3 Newsletter

Newsletters are another important tool for creating engagement and advising stakeholders on the project’s updates. Newsletters and email marketing can serve a number of purposes. They can create or increase awareness, provide basic information such as details of upcoming events and insights from the past ones, or create a sense of stability and commitment to the project by sharing its achievements and relevant messages to the stakeholder’s community. With insights and news, this tool can increase the visibility of agrifoodTEF and its services.

agrifoodTEF developed a branded newsletter on Mailchimp, with a submission form in the website homepage, in order to ease the affiliation. The newsletter is planned to be sent and published on the website quarterly, unless there are special needs from the project. The periodic newsletters will mainly outline the updates - such as recent participation in events or upcoming ones - together with an update on the new services and infrastructures available on the agrifoodTEF catalogue.

The 1st Newsletter has been focused on the introduction of the new Catalogue of Service and the new webpage of agrifoodTEF Nodes, together with a dedicated section on news and updates - with some outcomes from the Synergy Days in Barcelona and an update on the next upcoming webinar.

The project newsletters will be available on the website, with a dedicated webpage collecting all the editions.

Figure 22 – newsletter subscription on the agrifoodTEF website

Figure 23 – some printscreens from the 1st agrifoodTEF newsletter

6.1.4 Event management

To build a consolidated network of relevant stakeholders and promote agrifoodTEF’s objectives, the project organises and participates in events and engagement activities, including agrifoodTEF workshops, webinars, and third-party events. The format of these events included virtual, in-person, and hybrid activities. The paragraphs below detail all these engagement activities.

6.1.4.1 agrifoodTEF workshops

Workshops within the agrifoodTEF project serve as technical forums where experts convene to explore ideas and propose solutions to technical challenges. These workshops take various forms, including face-to-face (F2F), hybrid, or online formats. Workshops can vary widely in format, ranging from small group discussions to large-scale events, and can cover diverse topics, from skill development to strategy planning. Within the agrifoodTEF project, workshops play a crucial role for several reasons:

- **Collaboration and Networking:** Workshops bring together stakeholders, partners, and experts involved in a project. They provide a platform for collaboration and networking, fostering stronger ties among participants.
- **Knowledge Transfer:** Workshops facilitate the exchange of knowledge, ideas, and best practices. They create an environment where participants can share their expertise and learn from each other.

- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Involving stakeholders in workshops ensures their active participation and engagement in project activities. This can lead to a more inclusive and comprehensive project implementation.
- **Project Visibility:** Workshops can contribute to the visibility of a project by showcasing its achievements, innovations, and impact. This is essential for dissemination and outreach efforts.
- **Feedback and Evaluation:** Workshops offer an opportunity to gather feedback from participants, which can be valuable for project evaluation and improvement. They provide a structured space for reflection on project progress.

Among the workshops organised and attended by the agrifoodTEF team, one crucial one is represented by the Synergy Days, that took place from 13 to 15 October 2024 in Barcelona. The agrifoodTEF team hosted three workshops at the Synergy Days event, highlighting advancements in AI and robotics for the agrifood sector. Across two days, agrifoodTEF provided innovative insights into its pioneering work supporting SMEs, fostering digital skill development, and prioritising ethical data use.

- **Workshop nr.1: Validation Services for SMEs leveraging AI and Robotics in the agrifood sector**

The first workshop showcased practical examples of agrifoodTEF's validation services for SMEs, where partners demonstrated the innovative digital solutions they have developed. A highlight was given by the CEO of Microfy.AI, who shared how her company is integrating agrifoodTEF's services into their software and the positive impact it is having. Her presentation inspired other SMEs to consider leveraging agrifoodTEF's offerings to enhance their solutions.

- **Workshop nr.2: How can agrifoodTEF help EDIHs support SMEs?**

In the second workshop, co-organised with the [European Digital Innovation Hubs \(EDIH\)](#), agrifoodTEF explored ways to create accessible training materials for industries and farmers interested in adopting digital agritech solutions. The session identified specific topics and content formats needed for new training materials, set to be available soon on the agrifoodTEF Training Platform.

- **Workshop nr.3: Assessing Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects (ELSA) of digital technologies**

The final workshop, held in collaboration with [Data4Food2030](#), addressed the Ethical, Legal, and Social Aspects (ELSA) of using data. As agrifoodTEF's services involve extensive data handling, this session focused on ensuring that all data practices respect user privacy and adhere to essential ethical and legal standards.

The main outcomes from the Synergy Days' participations have been summarised in a dedicated [news piece](#), accessible on the agrifoodTEF website and a [recap video](#), published on YouTube.

Figure 24 – some printscreens of the agrifoodTEF recap video at Synergy Days

6.1.4.2 agrifoodTEF webinars

Webinars are central to enable a smooth transition from physical events to virtual events and offer the chance of presenting cutting-edge results of agrifoodTEF.

The main strategic goals of the webinars are linked to the promotion of the agrifoodTEF objectives, its digital solutions, its business model and the cooperation established with EDIHs.

The first agrifoodTEF webinar, scheduled for 18 December 2024, aims to foster knowledge-sharing and provide valuable resources to agrifood stakeholders. This session offers an in-depth introduction to agrifoodTEF's objectives, services, and support systems. This introductory webinar, the first of a series, features presentations from the project coordinator and project officer, and it will also include detailed guidance on how to apply to agrifoodTEF and access financial support through three of its nodes: Austria, Belgium, and Italy. The one-hour webinar, hosted on Zoom, is recorded for future access and published on the project's website and YouTube channel.

The webinar agenda and contributions were developed in collaboration with communications representatives from each node.

In order to give relevance to the work presented during the webinars, the communication team is going to take care of pre- and post-webinar promotional, outreach, and dissemination activities, that include:

- Creation of branded graphics;
- Development of a dedicated registration page on the agrifoodTEF website;
- Tailored email campaigns targeting relevant stakeholders;
- Regular social media promotion;

- Live tweeting during the event;
- Upload and release of the recorded webinar on the agrifoodTEF website and YouTube channel;
- Post-webinar news articles published on the website;
- Repurposing webinar content for ongoing social media campaigns in the following weeks.

The figures below present some of the activities performed to promote the 1st webinar.

Figure 25 – banners to promote the 1st webinar

Figure 26 – Cards developed to promote the 1st webinar on social media channels

Figure 27 – examples of promotional posts in different languages

The 1st webinar attracted 87 people from 24 countries. Their area of expertise spans from research to technology provision, as shared in the Figures below.

Figure 28 – countries of the experts who registered for the webinar

Figure 29- area of expertise of people attracted by the webinar

6.1.4.3 agrifoodTEF at 3rd-party events

Participation in third-party events is crucial for agrifoodTEF to achieve its goals and expand its impact. Since 2023, the agrifoodTEF consortium has attended over 15 events across Europe, actively engaging with stakeholders and promoting the project. These engagement activities serve multiple purposes, including:

- **Networking opportunities:** Building connections with industry leaders, stakeholders, and potential collaborators in the agritech and AI fields.
- **Staying updated:** Gaining insights into the latest advancements, challenges, and trends in the agritech sector, ensuring the project remains aligned with current developments.
- **Promoting agrifoodTEF:** Showcasing the project through booths, stands, and promotional materials, highlighting its mission, services, and innovations.
- **Knowledge sharing:** Presenting agrifoodTEF's objectives, progress, and contributions during panel discussions, presentations, and technical sessions.
- **Identifying synergies:** Exploring collaboration opportunities with other projects, organisations, companies, and stakeholders to amplify impact and foster innovation.

By participating in these events, agrifoodTEF enhances its visibility, strengthens its position as a key player in the agritech sector, and ensures meaningful engagement with the community.

Below is an overview of the 3rd-party events attended by agrifoodTEF partners in 2024.

Nr.	Date and Location	Name	Partners involved	Impact
1	21 February 2024, Belgium	OESO summit	ILVO	Presenting the agrifoodTEF project to potential new customers
2	27 February 2024, Finland	EUFRRAS Annual Assembly 2024	RISE	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers

3	8 – 10 March 2024, Poland	AGROTECH	Lukasiewicz	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
4	12 – 14 March 2024, Norway	Marketing agrifoodTEF and the Swe-sat in Norway	RISE	Presenting the agrifoodTEF project to potential new customers
5	19 – 20 March 2024, Poland	Europejskie Forum Rolnicze 2024	WOSRP	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
6	3 April 2024, Germany	TEF open for business	Josephinum	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
7	22 – 24 April 2024, Prague (Czech Republic)	Machine Learning Prague	Poland	Presenting the agrifoodTEF project to potential new customers
8	10 May 2024, Belgium	Research to Reality	ILVO	Presenting the agrifoodTEF project to potential new customers
9	11 May 2024, Poland	Szczyt EPI	Lukasiewicz, PSNC	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
10	15 May 2024, Sweden	Framtidens Jordbruk	RISE	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
11	18 – 19 May 2024, Poland	ZIELONE AGRO SHOW Ujęź	Lukasiewicz, PSNC, WOSRP	Presenting the agrifoodTEF project to potential new customers
12	23 May 2024, Spain	EDIH Network - Agrifood Thematic Working Group: kick-off meeting	DIH	Discussions on possible cooperation opportunities between EDIH agrifoodTEF
13	22 – 23 May 2024, Poland	Infoshare	Lukasiewicz, PSNC, WOSRP	Presenting the agrifoodTEF project to potential new customers
14	24 May 2024, the Netherlands	The impact of artificial intelligence on farm animals workshop	WUR	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
15	30 May 2024, the Netherlands	Future Farming Food Experience	WUR	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
16	18 June 2024, Belgium	Agritechdag 2024	ILVO	Presenting the agrifoodTEF project to potential new customers
17	4 – 5 June 2024, Poland	ITM	Lukasiewicz, PSNC, WOSRP	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
18	11 – 14 June 2024, Poland	56th International Symposium on Forestry Mechanization (FORMEC)	Lukasiewicz, PSNC, WOSRP	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
19	26 June 2024, Sweden	Borgeby Fältdagar	RISE	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
20	3 – 4 July 2024, Sweden	Brunnby Lantbrukardagar	RISE	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers

21	5 – 8 September 2024, Austria	AgriTier	Josephinum	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
22	9 September 2024, Poland	"Startupy w Pałacu"	Lukasiewicz, PSNC, WOSRP	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers among start-ups
23	10 September 2024, the Netherlands	Breda Robotics	WUR	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
24	18 September 2024, Italy	Innovazione AI-based per la trasformazione digitale: soluzioni innovative e ad alta efficienza per le PMI del Trentino in agricoltura, manifattura e digitalizzazione	FBK	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers among SMEs
25	20 – 23 September 2024, Poland	Agroshow Bednary	Lukasiewicz, PSNC, WOSRP	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
26	26 September 2024, Poland	Polagra	PSNC	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
27	4 October 2024, Poland	Współpraca Producentów Rolnych sposobem na Rozwój Rolnictwa i Obszarów Wiejskich	Lukasiewicz, PSNC, WOSRP	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
28	12 October 2024, France	Séminaire AgroTIC – Comment réussir le passage à grande échelle de la robotique en agriculture?	INRAE	Presenting the agrifoodTEF project to potential new customers
29	14 – 15 October 2024, Poland	AI Summit	Lukasiewicz, PSNC, WOSRP	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
30	14 - 15 October 2024, Barcelona (ES)	Synergy Days 2024	FBK, WUR, LNE, ILVO, RISE, TRUST-IT, PSNC	Networking and organisation of workshops and updates on TEF and the importance of TEFs
31	16 - 18 October 2024, Jönköping (SE)	Elmia Agriculture	RISE	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
32	17 October 2024, Online	How Can We Support SMEs Together with EDIHs Polska?	Lukasiewicz, PSNC, WOSRP	Webinar to promote cooperation and identify fresh innovation opportunities in the agrifood sector, synergies between agrifoodTEF and EDIHs Poland
33	24 October 2024, Poland	Nauka na rzecz zrównoważonego rozwoju	Lukasiewicz, PSNC, WOSRP	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
34	5 - 7 November 2024,	4th Annual Conference for EIP Operational Groups	Lukasiewicz	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers

	Łódź (PL)			
35	6 November 2024, the Netherlands	Info meeting for Dutch ministries	WUR	Meeting with Dutch ministries to share the latest advancements of agrifoodTEF
36	6 - 10 November 2024, Bologna (IT)	EIMA 2024 - International Exhibition for Gardening and Agricultural Equipment	FBK, POLIMI	Participation in sessions as panel speakers, networking and updates on agritech
37	6 November 2024, Belgium	Flanders AI Forum	ILVO	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
38	6 – 7 November 2024, Belgium	Crop Care day Kverneland	ILVO	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
39	12 November 2024, Vanves (FR)	2024 Artificial Intelligence Forum	LNE	Participating, presenting TEF and networking
40	13 - 14 November 2024, Madrid (ES)	VII DATAGRI Forum for digital transformation of the agri-food sector	Gradiant, DIH DATAlife, UCO, UDL, Hispatec	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
41	18 - 19 November 2024, Krakow (PL)	4th Central European Technology Forum (CETEF'24)	Lukasiewicz	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
42	26 - 28 November 2024, Bordeaux (FR)	Vinitech SIFEL 2024	IFV	Networking, booth and hosting conferences and workshops
43	26 - 27 November 2024, Brussels (BE)	EDIH Network Summit 2024	ILVO	Discussions on establishing concrete cooperations between EDIHs and TEFs
44	26 – 29 November 2024, Denmark	Agromek	DTI	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers
45	27 - 28 November 2024, Wels (AT)	Panorama 2024	JR	Presenting TEFs and networking
46	28 November 2024, Brussels (BE)	EIT Digital - AgriTech: Digital innovation for a sustainable European Agri-Food sector	FBK	Presenting TEFs as a panelist and networking
47	2 December 2024, Wageningen (NL)	Pursuing sustainability in food systems through AI innovation	WUR	Presenting the agrifoodTEF project to potential new customers

48	4 December 2024, Livorno (IT)	Progetto WAINE: Intelligenza Artificiale nelle PMI: Imminenti Sfide e opportunità'	TRUST-IT	Scouting synergy opportunities to enroll more SMEs to test and validate digital solutions in Italy
49	10 December 2024, United Kingdom	ESA webinar ' Commercial applications of SPace-Enabled Robotics: Agriculture'	WUR	Scouting new funding opportunities for agritech companies
50	10 December 2024, France	Séminaire AgroTIC – Comment réussir le passage à grande échelle de la robotique en agriculture?	DTI	Networking opportunities to scout new potential customers

Table 7 – 3rd-party events attended by the agrifoodTEF members

6.1.5 Communication elements

In the pursuit of amplifying the outreach and impact of the agrifoodTEF project a range of communication elements has been crafted to convey its message effectively. They are all described in detail in the following paragraphs.

6.1.5.1 Newspieces and press releases

Regular news pieces and press releases are key tools for keeping stakeholders, media, and the public informed about the latest developments, achievements, and milestones of agrifoodTEF. All news pieces and press releases have been developed in English to ensure broad accessibility and dissemination.

Since September 2024, with the launch of the new website, the agrifoodTEF team has published four news articles covering the project’s mission and objectives, highlights from participation in key events, in-depth analyses of TEFs and advancements in agritech, and more. These news pieces have been promoted through targeted social media campaigns to broaden their reach and engage the community, and they have also been included in the project's newsletter.

Blog & Insights

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NEWS

agrifoodTEF showcases AI and Robotics Innovations in agrifood at the Synergy Days

From 13 to 15 October 2024, the agrifoodTEF team hosted three workshops at the Synergy...

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Agriculture and Technology: How digital solutions will alter traditional agriculture

Agriculture is only one of the numerous industries that have seen significant change in...

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NEWS

agrifoodTEF– Europe's answer to digital revolution in the agricultural sector

Highlights from AgrifoodTEF's Press Conference: Highlighting Our Capabilities On July 12th...

Posted on: 04 October 2024

Figure 30 – Newspiece section on the agrifoodTEF website

Press releases play a key role in agrifoodTEF’s communication strategy, serving as official statements to raise awareness about the project’s mission and accomplishments. They are published on the agrifoodTEF website and promoted through a network of media channels specialising in technology, artificial intelligence, agriculture, and environmental topics. agrifoodTEF conducts targeted email marketing campaigns to disseminate press releases to maximise visibility. These campaigns are directed at media outlets, institutions, and organisations within the agricultural sector, ensuring the project reaches relevant and influential audiences. This approach ensures that agrifoodTEF maintains a steady flow of communication, enhancing its visibility and fostering stakeholder engagement.

In September 2024, the team has shaped the first [Press Release](#) of the project. The PR explained the main objectives of the project and was shared with 50 Press Agencies to be promoted.

European agritech companies harness the power of artificial farming for business

EU funds a new cutting-edge project

PRIVAS RELEASE

The EU-funded agrifoodTEF project empowers European agritech companies by providing access to advanced AI and robotics... (text continues)

Background

The same time as the European agritech companies and communities have had access to support from the European Commission for their AI, robotics and other technological services... (text continues)

The main goal of agrifoodTEF is to help agritech companies assess the full benefits of AI and AI-powered robotics technologies... (text continues)

According to Bettina Giallombardo, Chief of Science and Innovation at the agrifoodTEF project coordinator... (text continues)

"These services will have a strong impact that will help bridge the gap between research that happens in the research centers of the partners, who are involved in the consortium, and the market." Giallombardo says.

The services of TEF can be customized for each individual agritech company. The main goal is to connect small and medium size companies (SMEs) that can access available relations in the Catalogue of Services, a large database containing more than 200 AI services, for the companies to choose from.

agrifoodTEF is a good example of the direction in which Masia D'Algho, former Italian vice-minister and former president of the European Central Bank, wants the Union to develop. In a report published in September 2024, D'Algho calls for better cooperation in the agricultural sector between government, industry and academia, and for barriers to commercialisation to be removed.

Read about the project in a nutshell

- The European AI and Robotics Testing and Experimental Facilities, TEF's, help companies to test new technologies.
- The agritech centers TEF's, exist in 9 European countries: Italy, France, Denmark, Austria, Belgium, Poland, Sweden, The Netherlands, Spain.
- For agritech companies there is a catalogue containing more than 200 AI services. Already 50 have been delivered by its partners to small and medium sized companies, SMEs.
- The 5 year long project was launched in 2023.
- The total funding for the project is €60 million. The EU Commission is providing €30 million, with the remaining €30 million coming from the participating EU countries.

For further information

The agrifoodTEF project invites all interested parties to join its commitment to promoting AI and robotics solutions in the agrifood sector. To stay updated on agrifoodTEF progress and achievements, follow us on social media and our official website. For any inquiries, feel free to contact us at agrifood@tef.eu.

X: @AgrifoodTEF
YouTube: agrifoodTEF
LinkedIn: agrifoodTEF

Instagram: agrifood_tef
Facebook: AgrifoodTEF
Zenodo: agrifoodTEF
Website: www.agrifoodtef.eu

Figure 31 – Press Release shared with the Press Agencies

6.1.5.2 Success stories

A series of success stories has been planned to showcase concrete examples of services and products supported by agrifoodTEF. The goal is to highlight at least one success story from each Node. These stories serve multiple purposes, providing detailed insights into agrifoodTEF's impact while promoting the companies and innovations involved.

The outcome of these Success Stories is multifaceted, including:

- Dedicated web pages on the agrifoodTEF website, featuring articles in a dedicated section.
- Video interviews with companies that collaborated with agrifoodTEF, offering an in-depth look at their experiences and achievements.

A series of Success Stories are going to be developed per each node. The first Success Story was recorded in November 2024 with the Italian Node, featuring GeoInference, followed by a story from Austria, highlighting Farming Revolutions. The final version of the Success Stories is going to be shared both on the agrifoodTEF and YouTube's channel from January 2025.

Figure 32 – printscreens from the recording of the Success Stories

Development of Success Stories

To ensure quality and consistency, a structured process was implemented:

- Preparation of questions: tailored to capture key insights about the company, its services, and the outcomes of its collaboration with agrifoodTEF.
- Coordination with Node communication leads: the Nodes proposed success story candidates and collaborated closely to align and schedule company interviews.
- Rehearsal meetings: essential to refine questions and ensure the interview runs smoothly.
- Interviews recording: held via Zoom, featuring representatives from both agrifoodTEF and the company, providing multiple perspectives.

Each Success Story results in:

- Editorial content for the agrifoodTEF website, offering a comprehensive overview of the service, the company, customers' needs, the solutions provided, and the resulting impact on the industry.
- Branded video interviews, promoted through the agrifoodTEF website, YouTube channel, and social media channels for broader dissemination.

By creating content-rich articles and visually engaging videos, these Success Stories amplify agrifoodTEF's visibility while celebrating the achievements of its collaborators within the agrifood sector.

6.1.5.3 Visuals and infographics

The branding and visual identity of agrifoodTEF were initially established in the first year of the project (as presented in the first version of the deliverable D5.1). Building on the foundation laid by the original visual branding and color scheme, the project team developed a range of visuals and templates to ensure consistency and alignment with the established identity.

Theme and Colour Scheme

The partners chose a green-themed colour palette to reflect the project's connection to the agricultural sector. Green, universally associated with nature and sustainability, creates a direct visual link to the agricultural theme and underscores agrifoodTEF's commitment to fostering innovation within this domain. The colour choice reinforces the project's focus on sustainable practices and solutions, aligning its visual identity with its core mission and values.

Zoom Background

To maintain a consistent and professional appearance during virtual meetings, a Zoom background was designed in accordance with the agrifoodTEF theme. This universal and homogeneous background is available for use by consortium members and partners, providing a clear and recognisable affiliation with agrifoodTEF. By leveraging this branded visual, the project ensures that its identity remains prominent and cohesive across all virtual interactions. The integration of carefully chosen branding elements highlights agrifoodTEF's dedication to professionalism, coherence, and its roots in the agricultural and technological innovation sectors.

Figure 33 – agrifoodTEF's Zoom Background

Fliers

Given the complexity and technical nature of the content within the agrifoodTEF initiative, it was crucial to develop visually appealing yet straightforward and comprehensible materials. To achieve this, the project team created fliers featuring clear visuals and infographics designed to capture attention and effectively communicate the key objectives of agrifoodTEF and its nodes. These elements ensure that viewers can quickly grasp the most important points at a glance.

- **Design Approach**

The fliers were crafted to balance industry-specific information with accessibility, presenting the project's goals and activities in a way that resonates with diverse audiences. The design incorporates clean layouts, vibrant yet professional graphics, and concise messaging, all aimed at maximising engagement and comprehension.

To ensure the content is accurate, the team has implemented an internal validation process. The communication team develops the structure and texts, which are then reviewed and approved by members of the communication team at node level.

Initially, the texts are provided in English, but node leaders have the option to translate them into local languages, making the fliers more appealing to non-native speakers.

The fliers are created in two formats: a printable version for distribution at physical events and a web version available for download.

As of December 2024, 10 fliers have been developed to present the agrifoodTEF and its nodes main objectives. They are all accessible through Zenodo:

- General flier: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13950933>
- Austrian node: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13950380>
- Belgian node: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13950756>
- Dutch node: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13950782>
- French node: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13950809>
- Italian node: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951014>
- Polish node: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951035>
- Spanish node: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951057>
- Swedish node: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951072>

Figure 34 – Example of a general flier

Social Media Graphics and Banners

The project team developed a suite of graphics for use on social media channels, ensuring alignment with agrifoodTEF's visual identity. These graphics prominently feature the signature colours of agrifoodTEF, the project logo, and the co-funded logo of the European Commission. This consistent visual approach reflects the project's unity, adherence to its objectives, and commitment to transparency.

- [Design Principles for Social Media Posts](#)

The social media graphics were designed to harmonise with the project's overall branding. The choice of images was particularly significant, with visuals carefully selected to be relevant and directly connected to agrifoodTEF’s objectives and services. For instance, images included in posts often matched those used in related events, news articles, or website announcements. This created a cohesive and harmonious experience for viewers, reinforcing the connection between the content and its source.

- Banners and Backgrounds

The materials developed for banners and backgrounds across social media channels were crafted to maintain consistency with agrifoodTEF’s thematic style. These visuals incorporated the signature shapes, icons, and colours of the brand. The project logo, provided in two colour variations, ensured adaptability and optimal visibility across various platforms and backgrounds.

The following example shows the material that has been used as banners or backgrounds on the different social media channels.

Figure 35 – Example of social media header

Figure 36 – Examples of social media banners in square and rectangular versions

6.1.5.4 Videos

Videos are an important way to engage with the stakeholders as they generate more than 1200% shares than text and images combined on social media channels².

Videos are composed of images and audio and the union of these two aspects makes the video content more accessible and easier to understand. Thanks to this, videos represent an extremely useful instrument to engage with relevant stakeholders.

A series of videos have been produced and are going to be produced to promote agrifoodTEF, including:

- 3 general videos about the agrifoodTEF's objectives.
- 4 videos to present the nodes.

In addition to this, the team has additional video in the pipeline:

- 10 videos to present the nodes leaders and the digital solutions developed by each country
- Success Stories videos to present in a compelling way the work developed by the nodes in cooperation with some of its customers.

The videos released, including webinar recordings, are going to be published on the agrifoodTEF YouTube channel and promoted on the project's social media channels.

In order to increase the number of their visualisations, Ads Campaigns might be launched. Ads Campaigns are an excellent paid tool that works on keywords and offers the possibility to show the videos to potential stakeholders who search online for the keywords selected for the campaign. In addition, the Ads campaigns are from time to time called also Pay Per Click because the company pays only when a user clicks on the announcement.

The benefits offered by PPC campaigns are linked to the opportunity to sponsor the advertisements only to selected target customers and, as a consequence, the costs can be reduced. The targeting can be optimised by including relevant keywords, the topic of the video, demographic and interests of the audience.

6.2 Synergies

The agrifoodTEF project aims to foster collaboration and innovation across several critical areas of digital transformation in agriculture. By synergising with other European initiatives, the project team aims to accelerate the adoption of cutting-edge technologies, improve data integration, and enhance sustainable practices in the agritech sector. Below are the key areas where synergies are being developed:

²<https://vidico.com/news/video-marketing-statistics/>

1. Cloud-to-Edge Infrastructure and Services

AI applications in the agri-food sector depend on edge technology due to the challenges of uncertain communication in the field and the need for energy efficiency in agricultural machinery, robots, and drones. agrifoodTEF's nodes and satellites already provide robust testing and evaluation services for efficient cloud-to-edge AI solutions. These services will continue to expand, facilitating the deployment of advanced cloud-to-edge infrastructures and related services across the sector.

2. EU Common Data Space Strategy

The development of AI relies on access to high-quality training and benchmarking datasets, which can only be achieved through interconnected, sovereign data spaces. agrifoodTEF partners actively contribute to the development of the Common European Agricultural Data Space and lead the agriculture domains of several GAIA-X hubs in Europe. The project's datasets are interoperable with these initiatives, ensuring alignment with the Big Data Value Association (BDVA) and the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA). These collaborations maximise the impact of agrifoodTEF's data contributions.

3. AI-on-Demand Platform

In line with the Digital Europe Programme's vision for an AI-on-Demand platform, agrifoodTEF acts as a broker for high-quality AI and robotics solutions in the agri-food sector. Beyond testing and validating AI systems, the project provides access to pre-trained models and datasets as key sustainability assets. agrifoodTEF ensures compatibility with metadata standards and marketplaces defined by initiatives like GAIA-X to ensure interoperability.

4. European Excellence in Artificial Intelligence

agrifoodTEF supports Europe's commitment to AI excellence by creating conditions for AI development and adoption in the agri-food sector. Through testing and experimentation facilities, the project addresses societal challenges, such as sustainability and food security, highlighted in European strategic documents like the ELISE Research Agenda and national AI strategies.

5. Trustworthy AI Solutions for Society

The project aligns with the European Commission's focus on trustworthy AI with societal and economic benefits. agrifoodTEF provides facilities that ensure AI solutions in the agri-food sector are safe, transparent, and effective. By applying principles outlined also in global frameworks, like the Montreal Declaration and the Toronto Declaration, agrifoodTEF demonstrates how responsible AI development can address risks while securing food systems. Third-party conformity assessments developed within the project ensure alignment with European regulations for AI systems.

6. European Partnership for Agriculture of Data

agrifoodTEF actively supports the European Partnership for Agriculture of Data by contributing reference datasets to enhance policy monitoring and evaluation. These datasets combine Earth observation, environmental, and agricultural data to strengthen digital and data technologies for sustainable agriculture. By integrating with this partnership, agrifoodTEF amplifies its impact on sustainable agricultural practices across Europe.

7. Collaboration with European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs)

agrifoodTEF fosters synergies with the network of European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs) to accelerate the deployment of tested innovations in the agri-food sector. The project will connect common aspects, share best practices, and provide relevant training through its nodes.

This collaboration enables EDIHs to distribute innovations successfully tested within agrifoodTEF to the market more effectively. On the other side, by supporting EDIHs with targeted training and distribution channels, agrifoodTEF contributes to bridging the knowledge gap and fast-tracking innovation adoption in agriculture.

6.2.1 Role of agrifoodTEF with other TEF projects

agrifoodTEF aims to establish robust partnerships with other Testing and Experimentation Facilities (TEFs) projects, each addressing distinct aspects of AI and robotics innovation. These collaborations aim to share best practices, align methodologies, and collectively support Europe’s digital transformation. Key TEFs include:

- **TEF-Health:** focused on Health AI and robotics, TEF-Health provides technical and scientific support to Health AI providers and notified bodies, fostering innovation in healthcare solutions.
- **AI-MATTERS:** this initiative aims to enhance the resilience and flexibility of Europe’s manufacturing sector by integrating cutting-edge AI, robotics, and intelligent autonomous systems for adaptable production processes.
- **Citcom.AI:** aimed at testing AI in smart cities and communities, Citcom.AI bridges the gap between technology, infrastructure, and the citizens who interact with these systems, fostering urban innovation.

To ensure alignment among the TEF projects, the newly funded **CoordinaTEF** project supports coordination between these TEFs. CoordinaTEF focuses on measuring and harmonising key performance indicators (KPIs) across TEFs, linking them to client satisfaction and tangible outcomes.

This unified effort will foster the regular exchange of best practices and co-organisation of workshops and help align service offerings with the goals of Europe’s **Digital Transformation Acceleration** initiative, ensuring cutting-edge solutions meet industry and societal needs.

7. Monitoring

The impact of all strategically important communication and dissemination activities performed is measured through a core set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), whenever quantifiable. A continuous activity of monitoring is carried out by the project members on a monthly basis. Qualitative metrics come into play whenever there is a need for a deeper analysis of the relevance of outcomes achieved.

The table below shows the end of KPI targets and their status at M24.

KPI	Value at M24	Target M48
Participation in workshops with projects funded under the same call	21	40+
Total number of international events at a TEF node or satellite	40	40+
Total number of printed publications	8	50+
Distributed printed promotional materials	900	2000
number of stakeholders involved in agrifoodTEF activities	79	100+
Number of joint activities with other TEFs and EDIHs	2	20
Total number of posts published via social media (Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook, YouTube)	217	2000
number of European Countries from which agrifoodTEF will be accepting applications from and which will be included in the marketing, communication and dissemination strategy	9	30
Number of agrifoodTEF portal unique visitors per year	793	1000+

number of provided trainings in the catalogue	0 (the catalogue will be launched in 2025)	60+
Number of workshops on services update and optimization including smaller farms and businesses	37	40+

Table 8 – Communication and Dissemination KPIs

7.1 KPI dashboard

To monitor progress and assess performance, the team has developed a KPI dashboard using PowerBI. This dashboard consolidates all key performance indicators, including those related to communication and dissemination activities. It provides detailed insights into the performance of social media channels across the network of nodes, capturing data such as the number of posts, followers, countries, and specific social media platforms.

The evaluation of the KPI dashboard enables the team to track the performance of each country effectively and implement corrective actions where necessary to optimise results.

Future enhancements to the dashboard are planned, including the integration of total follower counts across all agrifoodTEF social media channels. Additionally, the website performance dashboard, currently managed through Google Analytics, will also be incorporated into the PowerBI platform for a more unified and efficient monitoring system.

Figure 37 – Social media KPI dashboard on PowerBI

7.2 Google analytics

While the integration of Google Analytics into PowerBI is underway, website analytics are currently monitored through a dedicated Google Analytics dashboard. This dashboard, developed in October 2024 following the website revamp, provides valuable insights into website performance. However, as it was built in October 2024, it should be noted that the data tracked does not cover the entire project lifecycle.

Tracking and analysing website activity and online interactions is essential for assessing the effectiveness of web marketing initiatives and optimizing the project’s outreach efforts. Tools like Google Analytics play a pivotal role in collecting and organizing this data into actionable metrics. Key indicators for agrifoodTEF’s online outreach strategy include:

- *Number of visits or sessions:* A visit is considered complete if a user remains inactive for more than 30 minutes.
- *Number of users or visitors:* Unique users are counted regardless of how often they return.
- *Pageviews:* Tracks the total number of pages viewed.
- *Views per page:* Highlights the frequency of visits to individual pages.
- *Bounce rate:* The percentage of visits where users only view one page before leaving.
- *Pages per visit:* Indicates the average number of pages viewed during a single visit.
- *Average visit duration:* Reflects the average time spent on the site across all visits during a given period.
- *Events:* Measures user interactions that align with project objectives, such as clicks, downloads, or form submissions.

These indicators are critical for assessing the success of online dissemination efforts. They provide actionable insights that enable the project to identify areas for continuous improvement across three key dimensions:

- **Graphics and Design:** Enhancing visual appeal and alignment with project branding.
- **Site Usability:** Ensuring intuitive navigation and accessibility for users.
- **Content and Communication:** Optimizing messaging and information delivery to engage the audience effectively.

Some printscreens of the main KPIs monitored through Google Analytics are summarised below.

Figure 38 – Top countries visiting the website

<u>PAGE TITLE AND SCREEN ...</u>	<u>VIEWS</u>
AgriFood	458
Catalogue of Services Agri...	359
About agrifoodTEF AgriFood	208
Empowering AI & Robotics i...	117
agrifoodTEF	114
Upcoming events AgriFood	85
Catalogue of Services agrif...	69

Figure 39 – Most viewed pages

<u>SESSION PRIMARY ...</u>	<u>SESSIONS</u>
Direct	94
Organic Search	119
Organic Social	29
Referral	27
Email	1

Figure 40 – Website visits aquisition

8. Conclusions and next steps

The 3rd version of agrifoodTEF Dissemination and Communication Plan and reports including network represents the cornerstone of every communication and dissemination activity to be carried out over the project’s lifetime and the foundations for exploiting and sustaining the results. As such, it has been developed and agreed-upon by all Partners involved in WP6.

It defines the strategy for communication, dissemination and stakeholder engagement and sets out plans for each core activity and helps evaluate the activities to be performed for reaching the goals and assessing impacts.

The main conclusions are:

- The current version of the plan is tightly linked to the project results. It is therefore is to be considered as a living document, enabling partners to update it on a yearly basis and whenever necessary.
- The document defines all strategic goals, including branding and defines its communication channels and levers.

- Dissemination and communication activities in the second year of the project's lifetime have included some improvements and changes in the way of working, compared to Y1, to achieve better results.
- The dissemination and communication activities are updated on a monthly basis through the KPI dashboard. The monitoring activity will help the team better track the activities performed and propose corrective actions, when needed.

In 2025, the team will continue implementing the communication and dissemination strategy outlined in the campaigns presented in Chapter 5. This includes strengthening the social media strategy at the node level and organising events aimed at attracting more SMEs, start-ups, and industrial players as potential customers of TEF services. Additionally, in collaboration with the consortium team, the goal is to develop and launch two new catalogues on the website: one featuring the training platform and another dedicated to infrastructure.

The release of the first set of success stories and videos will provide a comprehensive overview of TEF services, further promoting the project's primary objectives and attracting new potential customers.

